

Shop Tax Payment System for Township Development Affairs Department, Yamethin

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Abstract. The Shop Tax Payment System For Township Development Affairs Department, Yamethin, is an online platform developed using the MERN stack to assist township development departments in managing shop tax collections efficiently. It allows administrators to monitor user payments, issue warnings for overdue fees, and generate receipts, while shop users can securely log in, view owned shops, and check warnings and receipts. This system aims to replace traditional manual processes, ensuring timely payments, reducing administrative burden, and enhancing transparency between shops and the department staffs.

Keyword: MERN, Payment, Shop, Tax, Township.

INTRODUCTION

This system is very convenient for shop owners who cannot always go to the department in person [3]. This project focuses on designing a convenient shop tax payment system that allows shop users to check their warning, receive receipts, and stay updated online, even if they are not feeling well or are away from town. It reduces the need for paperwork and office visits, helping to avoid delays and making the process convenient for everyone. Administrators can manage users, assign shops, send warnings, and keep all records in one place with ease. The system aims to improve organization, save time, and create a more efficient and transparent tax management process. Overall, the goal is to provide a user-friendly, real-time platform that benefits both shop owners and the township department.

PROBLEM

Managing shop tax payments manually can be time-consuming and inefficient for both shop owners and township administrators. Many shop owners face difficulties in keeping track of payment deadlines, resulting in delays, confusion, and unnecessary penalties. Visiting the office for every update or issue is also inconvenient, especially for those who are busy, unwell, or living far away. Likewise, the department struggles with organizing records, sending reminders, and managing shop-user relationships effectively. To address these challenges, a system is needed that allows shop owners to access information anytime, receive updates in real-time, and make timely payments. This system aims to reduce paperwork, avoid misunderstandings, and create a more organized and transparent tax management process. In this project, the focus is mainly on designing and developing that digital solution.

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APPROACH

This system consists of two primary roles: Admin and User. Users must first log in to access the system’s core functionalities. Upon successful authentication, they are directed to a personalized dashboard, where they can submit shop tax payments, view previously accepted receipts, and check for any warnings issued by the admin. The system also allows users to securely log out, terminating their session and ensuring data protection.

On the administrative side, the admin is required to log in to access the admin dashboard, where they can manage and monitor user activities. Admin functionalities include accepting or rejecting payment submissions, checking overdue, issuing warnings, removing users from shops, and viewing or generating official payment receipts in PDF format. After that the admin can log out.

Figure 1: System Flow Diagram

Figure 2: Database Design

An Entity Relationship Diagram uses data modeling techniques that can help define business processes and serve as the foundation for a relational database. An ERD attribute can be denoted as a primary key, which identifies a unique attribute, or a foreign key, which can be assigned to multiple attributes. A cardinality notation can then define the attributes of the relationship between the entities. In the database, there are six collections. The collections are user, admin, payment, receipt, shop and warning. The figure 2 shows database design for all the data tables and their relationship of the database.

RESULTS

The design of each page in the Shop Tax Payment System has been carefully created to be simple and user-friendly. The system is intended for shop owners under the township development department to manage their tax payments conveniently. With just an internet connection on a mobile phone or any other device, users can log in to the system, submit payments, check past receipts, and read any warnings issued by the admin - without needing to visit the department physically. The system also includes an admin dashboard where authorized staff can monitor user payments, issue warnings for overdue taxes, and confirm transactions in real time. Since this system is built for users within a specific township, it does not support users from other locations. One limitation is that users must have internet access to use the system. However, in the future, improvements could be made to allow limited offline access

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or expand it to support multiple townships and other departments. Overall, this system provides a more organized, efficient, and direct way for shop users and township staff to manage tax responsibilities from online. This system is hosted on Railway, ensuring reliable cloud-based deployment and allowing both users and admins to access it from anywhere with an internet connection. Overall, the system provides a more organized, efficient, and direct way for shop users and township staff to manage tax responsibilities from online.

Figure 3: Home Page

Figure 4: System Report

CONCLUSION

The Shop Tax Payment System is implemented for the Township Development Affairs Department in Yamethin Township to streamline tax-related processes between shop owners and administrators. This system allows users to log in, view the dashboard, and submit monthly

tax payments, view warnings for overdue payments, access payment receipts, and log out- all through a simple and user-friendly web application. By automating and digitizing the payment workflow, this system significantly reduces manual errors, delays, and the need for in-person visits, ultimately promoting transparency and efficiency in local governance. In conclusion, this Shop Tax Payment System contributes to the modernization of public service delivery by offering a reliable platform for tax compliance and communication between shops and the Township Development Department.

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